

CCG POLICY BRIEF

Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Nuclear Power

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Summary

Nuclear power has historically been one of the largest sources of low-carbon electricity globally. Whilst it is expected to play a smaller role in the future electricity mix compared to renewables like wind and solar, it holds strong potential to provide low-carbon, baseload generation in countries which have the capabilities and expertise to deploy it, though over the last few decades its use has become increasingly politically contentious.

For these countries, the formulation of their strategy and deployment plans for nuclear power relies on technical insights gained from energy system models (ESMs), such as OSeMOSYS. However, there is growing public opposition to the deployment of nuclear power, which, combined with long lead times, high costs of electricity, and poor historical records of effective project delivery, raises questions over the role it will play in future electricity systems. Here, we discuss how global cost ranges for nuclear power taken from the open literature could be used to define and justify assumptions regarding the future cost of nuclear power, especially in countries and regions with outdated or no empirical data on the costs of deployment.

Key Policy Recommendations

- There are numerous other factors beyond just cost that need to be accounted for when modelling nuclear as a low-carbon technology in decarbonisation pathways, including safety, public opinion, and practical lead times.
- Academic researchers, government ministries, and other stakeholders operating in countries with outdated or no empirical data on nuclear power should conduct scoping studies to understand its costs.
- Global cost ranges for nuclear power from the literature can be a useful tool to situate cost assumptions for ESMs, but are not a substitute for direct engagement with industry stakeholders.

Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling of Nuclear Power

Introduction

Nuclear power has historically been one of the largest sources of low-carbon electricity generation and is expected to complement wind and solar photovoltaic power as a dispatchable low-carbon source of electricity that does not suffer from intermittency issues. The International Energy Agency predicts in its Stated Policies Scenario that the installed capacity globally could increase by nearly 50% to 612 GW in 2050 from an existing 417 GW in 2022 [1]. The development of small modular reactors and other advanced reactor designs could increase the potential role that nuclear power will play in the future electricity system.

However, nuclear power has long been contentious both politically and economically. Long lead times and substantial cost overruns have led to high costs of electricity from nuclear power, whilst activist and campaigning groups have raised concerns about the radioactive waste created by nuclear processes (which can remain radioactive and dangerous to humans for thousands of years). Despite its role as the second-largest source of low-carbon power globally, there is still substantial uncertainty over the future deployment and costs of nuclear power. Global attitudes to nuclear power suffered a marked shift after the Fukushima disaster in Japan in 2011. Future growth is expected to mainly be focused in China and other developing markets, though it is expected to face challenges in some regions competing against lower cost and faster to install technologies such as solar and wind.

The costs of new build nuclear reactors vary substantially, with the International Energy Agency and Nuclear Energy Agency finding that in 2020 the overnight costs of new nuclear capacity varied from a low of 2,157 USD/kW in South Korea to a high of 6,920 USD/kW in Slovakia [2], a ratio of over 3.2. This highlights the importance of selected project specific estimates of capital costs when modelling nuclear as a potential technology in energy system models (ESMs), especially given the range of reactor types currently available. Due to multilateral agreements on the proliferation of nuclear technologies, there are also limited countries in which nuclear power can be deployed. This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (eg total installed cost, operating costs, operational lifetimes) which are key to modelling the cost of nuclear power, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for nuclear power, whilst providing energy system modellers and other stakeholders with a method of situating and justifying their cost assumptions in the absence of empirical data. Data on the cost of nuclear power also plays a key role in informing the political debate around the use of nuclear technologies, though there are many other factors (e.g., safety, long-term sustainability) that may play a more important role in the political discussion.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on nuclear power were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy systems modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS [3]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers the range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of nuclear power, including historical and projected data of operating costs, capital costs, construction times and total operational lifetime. The dataset has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link:

<https://zenodo.org/records/10893938>.

Global current capital costs for nuclear power

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital costs for the deployment of nuclear power, taken across 2020–2024. Generation III designs cover Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR), Light Water Reactors (LWR), Pressurized Heavy Water Reactors (PHWR) such as the CANDU, and the Vodo-Vodyanoi Energetichesky Reaktor (VVER); Generation III+ designs covers the European Pressurized Reactor (EPR) and Advanced Light Water Reactor (ALWR), such as the AP1000. SMR stands for Small Modular Reactor. The costs extracted from the open literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 7,571, 9,751, and 8,822 USD/kW for Gen III, Gen III+ and SMRs. Data that were found in the open literature were predominantly from the handful of states with civil nuclear capabilities, with substantial data gaps on what the cost of deploying nuclear could hypothetically be for countries without nuclear power capabilities. Whilst there are international agreements and processes that limit the spread of nuclear technologies (even those used solely for nuclear power, given risks around their dual-use for weapons production), nuclear power is expected to grow in countries open to its use . [1] .

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs for nuclear power stations in 2020–2024, for each category. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range, and outliers are shown with diamonds. The 25th, 50th, and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar.

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Nuclear power will continue to play a key role in the supply of low-carbon electricity globally, though most scenarios predict that it will complement the supply of low-carbon electricity from wind and solar over the next decade globally [1]. Understanding the potential costs of deployment, especially in countries where there has been no prior deployment and who are seeking the support of nuclear states in deploying nuclear power, will be key to the development of appropriate integrated energy and climate strategies. Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available) and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050. As demonstrated by **Error! Reference source not found.**, the majority of countries and regions across the globe have limited or non-existent deployment of nuclear power, causing data availability issues for technoeconomic parameters such as installation or financing costs that are key to the effective understanding of the costs of deploying nuclear power. These data gaps create significant difficulties for energy system modellers around the selection and justification of cost assumptions for nuclear power.

Figure 2: Range of operating costs for nuclear power stations in a) 2020–2024 for each world region, where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050.

Whilst political attitudes and concerns around nuclear power are valid, the debate over nuclear power's role in future energy systems needs to be informed by accurate, up to date information on technology cost and performance. This is especially important with the development of Small Modular Reactors, which could lead to a much more widespread use of nuclear power (especially in countries with limited or no deployment of nuclear power). Understanding the potential costs will be crucial to defining national nuclear strategies and goals for nuclear deployment.

In countries and regions with limited deployment of nuclear power, it is important for energy system modellers to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling, as the decarbonisation pathways and technical insights developed from modelling may be highly sensitive to the costs of nuclear power. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in energy system models (ESMs) for these countries against empirical data taken from other countries and regions, addressing the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of energy and climate strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of nuclear power, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of nuclear power. Engagement with other stakeholder groups, especially local communities, can help raise concerns around nuclear power and ensure that efforts are taken to account for these in ESM and the development of energy policy.

Conclusions

Despite set-backs over the last decade, nuclear power is expected to still play a substantial role in the energy transition. With the support of nuclear states, nuclear power could be developed in countries which do not yet have nuclear technology capabilities. Data on the expected costs of deploying nuclear power in countries without nuclear capabilities is limited, with projects in nuclear states suffering from cost overruns and long lead times. Concerns about safety and sustainability from local communities and other stakeholder groups may also interact with economic factors to limit the deployment of nuclear power. Accounting for these factors and addressing the challenges around economic data availability will be crucial to accurate ESM to inform energy policy. There is a need to recognise the sensitivity of ESMs to assumptions regarding the costs of nuclear power as well as to prioritise transparency and data sharing and to justify cost assumptions in regions with limited empirical data. In so doing, stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and reliability of the scenarios generated from ESMs, ensuring their accuracy, utility, and relevance to policy. Whilst global ranges from the open literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with private sector stakeholders will be essential for understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios.

References

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